

Factors Affecting the Health Behaviors of Tobacco-Addicted Academic and Administrative Staff Working at the University

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to determine the factors influencing the health behaviors of tobacco-addicted university academic and administrative personnel based on the Health Belief Model. The study sample criteria were academic and administrative staff working at Istanbul Beykent University, where the necessary permissions were obtained, tobacco addicts, and those who agreed to participate in the study. Fifty-four individuals who met the inclusion criteria were included in the study. Descriptive statistics, the Mann-Whitney U test, the Kruskal-Wallis test, the chi-square test, and logistic regression analysis were used. A significance level of $p < 0.05$ was accepted. The study identified relationships among health status, addiction level, reasons for starting smoking, and self-efficacy. The findings revealed that the majority of participants were aware of the negative effects of smoking on health, believed quitting smoking was beneficial, and had a low addiction level. However, it was determined that the immediate social environment played a decisive role in smoking, and that as addiction level increased, health risks were perceived as more serious. Perception of self-efficacy has been found to be a significant factor in smoking cessation behavior, suggesting that interventions aimed at increasing individuals' self-confidence in their capabilities in smoking cessation programs may be effective. Based on these results, it is recommended that smoking cessation programs for university employees be supported with multidimensional approaches that target social environmental factors and self-efficacy levels, and that policies that reduce access to tobacco products and increase economic disincentives be maintained.

Keywords: Tobacco dependence, Health belief model, Health behavior, University staff

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Introduction

Tobacco use is a significant public health problem that threatens people's lives worldwide. Long-term tobacco use causes illness, disability, suffering, and, most importantly, death (World Health Organization [WHO], 2025). The main cause of tobacco addiction stems from the addictive effects of nicotine. Withdrawal symptoms occur after a period of abstinence (Selby & Zawertailo, L. 2022; Yeşilay, 2025). While tobacco consumption is most commonly through cigarette smoking, it is also used in many other ways, including hookah tobacco, cigar tobacco, pipe tobacco, rolled or heated tobacco, and smokeless tobacco products (WHO, 2025).

Tobacco usage is a major determinant of preventable diseases and deaths. Therefore, tobacco dependence holds a significant place within the “Sustainable Development Goals” under the framework of the “Global Action Plan for the Prevention and Control of Noncommunicable Diseases” (WHO, 2019). Globally, about 1.3 billion people use tobacco. The majority of these individuals reside in low- and medium-income countries (WHO, 2025). According to the World Health Organization's "Tobacco Trends 2000–2030" report, tobacco use is highest in the Southeast Asia region (26.5%), followed closely by the European region (25.3%). When analyzed by gender, cigarette consumption is found to be significantly higher among men compared to women (WHO, 2024). According to the 2016 data from the WHO Global Adult Tobacco Survey for Turkey, 19.2 million people in Turkey use cigarette products. This rate is higher amongst men (44.1%) than women (19.2%). The average number of cigarettes consumed per day is 18, and most smokers report using their first cigarette within 30 minutes of awakening. The same study showed that the average age of smoking initiation is 17. Moreover, 89.8% of adults believe that smoking causes serious diseases (WHO, 2016). According to the Turkish Statistical Institute (TURKSTAT), the proportion of individuals aged 15 and over who use tobacco products daily was 28.3% in 2022. This rate was found again to be higher among men compared to women (TURKSTAT, 2022).

There are numerous factors that impact an individual's tobacco use behavior. Variables such as gender, age, having family members or peers who smoke, marital status, education level, alcohol consumption, stress, income level, curiosity, and peer influence all influence individual health behaviors and can lead to significant health problems (Berberoğlu, Taşpınar & Öztaş, 2019; Carter et al., 2015; Çalışkan, 2015; Liu et al., 2019; Korkut & Sevinç, 2021; Merih et al., 2021; Özvurmaz & Yavaş, 2018). Health problems associated with tobacco use include cancer, stroke, cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, sudden infant death syndrome, acute respiratory infections, otitis media, respiratory diseases, asthma, emphysema, and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). It also increases the risk of some eye diseases, as well as immune system problems such as tuberculosis and rheumatoid arthritis. (Al-Bashaireh et al., 2018; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2020; Yeşilay, 2025). These health issues emerge as a result of risky health behaviors associated with tobacco addiction.

All forms of tobacco use have addictive potential and contribute to risky health behaviors by negatively affecting an individual's health practices. Utilizing model-based approaches is beneficial for assessing factors affecting health behaviors related to addiction, managing symptoms, and promoting positive health behaviors (Champion, 1984; Yılmaz Tuncay et al., 2019). The Health Belief Model (HBM) is often used to explain the factors that affect individuals' health behaviors. The core

components of the model include: Perceived Susceptibility (an individual's perception of the possibility of developing a disease), Perceived Severity (beliefs about the seriousness of the consequences if the condition is not treated), Perceived Benefits, Perceived Barriers, Cues to Action, Self-Efficacy (belief in one's ability to change behavior), and other modifying factors (sociodemographic and sociopsychological variables) (Champion & Skinner, 2008; Hayden, 2009; Gözüm & Çapık, 2014; Kurcer & Erdoğan, 2020). According to the model, assessing individuals' perceptions of tobacco use is the first step in raising awareness and promoting positive health behaviors. In fostering positive health behaviors regarding tobacco dependence, how individuals perceive the threat of tobacco use to their health, and their perceptions of benefits and barriers, play a critical role. In particular, the anxieties experienced by the individual, that is, the perception of obstacles (loss of friends, fear of gaining weight, inability to focus on work, missing cigarettes, etc.) have a negative impact on quitting tobacco use (Yılmaz Tuncay et al., 2019; Ünüvar & Dişçigil, 2017). Model-based interventions provide a holistic approach, especially for adults, and can contribute significantly to reducing preventable public health problems.

Method

Purpose and Type of the Study

This descriptive study was conducted between December 2024 and August 2025 with the aim of identifying the factors affecting health behaviors of tobacco-addicted academic and administrative university personnel based on the Health Belief Model.

Research Questions

The research questions are formulated in this study as follows:

1. What is the prevalence of tobacco dependence among academic and administrative university staff who are tobacco users?
2. What are the sociodemographic characteristics and tobacco-related characteristics of academic and administrative university staff who are tobacco users?
3. What are the factors affecting the health behaviors of tobacco-addicted academic and administrative university personnel?
4. How do tobacco-addicted academic and administrative university staff perceive the health risks associated with tobacco dependence?

Sample of the Study

The study was conducted at Istanbul Beykent University, located in the Büyükçekmece district of Istanbul. Without performing a formal sample size calculation, the study aimed to include tobacco-addicted academic and administrative personnel on a voluntary and random basis. Inclusion criteria for the study were as follows: being an academic or administrative staff member at Istanbul Beykent University (for which the necessary permissions were obtained), being addicted to tobacco, and agreeing to participate in the study. A total of 54 individuals who met the inclusion criteria were included in the study.

Data Collection

Prior to the study, institutional permission was obtained, and data were collected from academic and administrative personnel using online data collection tools. The data were collected through a Personal Information Form, developed by the researchers based on a review of the relevant literature, and the Fagerström Test for Nicotine Dependence.

Data Collection Tools

Personal Information Form:

This form was developed by the researchers based on a review of the literature (Selçuk & Mercan, 2017; Çifçi et al., 2018; Terzi et al., 2019; Kurcer & Erdoğan, 2020) and consists of 32 questions aimed at evaluating the sociodemographic characteristics and smoking-related behaviors of academic and administrative personnel.

Fagerström Test for Nicotine Dependence (FTND):

The scale was developed by Fagerström in 1989 to determine the level of physical addiction on nicotine (Fagerström & Schneider, 1989). The Turkish validation and reliability study of the six-item scale was conducted by Uysal et al. (2004) and the Cronbach's alpha coefficient was reported as 0.56.

Each item on the scale is scored between 0 and 3, with a total score ranging from 0 to 10. Higher scores indicate a greater level of nicotine addiction. Based on the total score obtained, nicotine addiction is classified into five categories: Very low dependence (0–2 points), Low dependence (3–4 points), Moderate dependence (5 points), High dependence (6–7 points), Very high dependence (8–10 points).

Data Analysis

The data was analyzed using the SPSS software package (version 25.0). Descriptive statistics, the Mann-Whitney U test, the Kruskal-Wallis test, the chi-square test, and logistic regression analysis were used in the study. A significance level of $p < 0.05$ was considered significantly significant.

Ethical Considerations

Institutional approval for the study was obtained from the Rectorate of Istanbul Beykent University (No: E-61952817-044-186126) and from the Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Committee for Social and Human Sciences of Istanbul Beykent University (Date: January 3, 2025, No: E-45778635-050.99-176541). Permission was granted for the use of the data collection tools in the study. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were also informed that they could withdrawal from the study at any time without any consequences.

Results

Describe Characteristics of the Participants

The average age of the staff included in the study was 30.7 years (min–max: 18–63). The majority of the participants were female (66.6%), working as administrative personnel (57.4%), and reported their income level as "moderate" (55.5%).

Most of the participants perceived their health condition as "very good/good" (79.6%). Regarding parental education, the majority of participants' mothers had either no formal education, did not complete primary school, or were primary school graduates (55.5%), whereas most of the fathers had completed high school, vocational school, or higher education (59.2%). (Table 1)

Among the participants, 8 individuals (15%) responded "Yes" to the question "Do you have a chronic illness?" These chronic conditions included asthma, bronchitis, supraventricular tachycardia (SVT), diabetes, celiac disease, hepatitis B, epilepsy, migraine, and allergic rhinitis. The majority of the staff (61.1%) started smoking after the age of 18, and 70.4% had been smoking for more than five years. Most mothers of the participants did not smoke (51.9%), while 37% of fathers smoked, and a large proportion of siblings/spouses (63%) were smokers." Additionally, most closest friends of the participants (92.6%) were smokers, and the primary reason for starting smoking was reported as pleasure/enjoyment (31.6%) (Table 2).

Regarding responses regarding health beliefs:

For the perceived susceptibility subscale, the majority answered "Yes" to the question "Are you worried about the negative effects of smoking on your health?" (74.1%), and also "Yes" to "Do you think you will become ill if you continue smoking?" (74.1%). However, most participants responded "No" (57.4%) to the question "Do advertisements or news about smoking concern you regarding your health?"

For the perceived severity subscale, most participants responded "No" (51.9%) to the question "Do you think you will become addicted to tobacco?" and "Yes" (72.2%) to the question "If you become ill, would you quit smoking?" Questions regarding the perceived benefit sub-dimension: The majority responded Yes (94.4%) to the question "Do you think quitting smoking is beneficial?", The majority responded Yes (75.9%) to the question "Do you think you will be healthy when you quit smoking?", The majority responded Yes (53.7%) to the question "Do you feel good when you think about quitting smoking?".

Regarding the barriers perceived subscale: The majority of participants responded "Yes" (72.2%) to the question "Do you think smoking is expensive?", "No" (92.6%) to "Does smoking embarrass you in social settings?", and "No" (96.3%) to "Do you think you will be excluded from your social circle if you quit smoking?"

Regarding the self-effectiveness subscale: The majority answered "Yes" to the questions "Is being healthy important to you?" (94.4%), "Do you want to stop smoking?" (68.5%), "Do you truly believe you can stop smoking?" (59.3%), "Is stopping smoking important to you?" (50%), and "Can you stop smoking with help?" (61.1%).

According to the responses to the Fagerström Nicotine Dependence Test, tobacco addiction levels were as follows: 32 individuals had very low dependence, 7 had low dependence, 6 had moderate dependence, 5 had high dependence, and 4 had very high dependence. The mean Fagerström Nicotine Dependency Test score was 2.61 ± 2.62 . Item means ranged between 1.05 ± 0.53 and 3.62 ± 1.29 . When comparing health perceptions across age groups in the study, the severity perception was higher in the 18-40 age group compared to the group over 41 years old. This difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). No significant differences were found between age groups concerning the mean

scores of other perceptions ($p > 0.05$). Females displayed a significantly higher severity perception compared to males ($p = 0.03$), with the difference being statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Individuals who believed in quitting smoking had significantly higher severity perception ($p = 0.008$) and self-effectiveness perception ($p = 0.000$) compared to those who did not believe. These differences were found to be highly significant ($p < 0.05$, $p < 0.001$). When the addiction level and perceptions were compared in the study, the perception of seriousness of those with High/Very high addiction levels was found to be higher than the others. The difference is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

When comparing the age of smoking initiation with descriptive characteristics, the group that started smoking after the age of 18 showed significantly higher health status and addiction levels. This difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The dependency among variables was also found to be statistically significant (Table 3).

Logistic regression analysis was conducted for factors related to the age of smoking initiation, revealing associations with health status (OR: 41.632, 95% CI: 3.442-503.6), addiction level (OR: 0.121, 95% CI: 0.029-0.499), reason for starting smoking (OR: 0.523, 95% CI: 0.286-0.956), and self-efficacy (OR: 2.334, 95% CI: 1.202-4.553). No meaningful associations were found for other variables (Tables 4 and 5).

Discussion

In this study, the predominance of women and administrative staff among participants reflects the general demographic structure of employees at the university, yet diverges from previous findings on tobacco use. National data in Türkiye indicate that men use tobacco products at higher rates than women (TURKSTAT, 2022). Similarly, the 2016 Global Adult Tobacco Survey conducted by the WHO reported prevalence of smoking 44.1% among men and 19.2% among women (WHO, 2016). The higher proportion of female participants in the present study may be attributed to the personnel distribution within the university as well as the voluntary nature of recruitment. However, recent research suggests that smoking among women, particularly young and working women, has been increasing, with the influence of traditional social norms on this behavior diminishing (Berberoğlu et al., 2019; Merih et al., 2021).

The majority of participants reported initiating smoking after the age of 18, a finding that differs from national studies showing initiation typically occurs between ages 15 and 19 (Çalışkan, 2015; Korkut & Sevinç, 2021). This may reflect later initiation among university personnel compared with students. Moreover, the fact that 70.4% of participants had been smoking for more than five years suggests a chronic pattern of nicotine addiction and reduced likelihood of cessation attempts. The literature supports this interpretation, noting that longer smoking duration is associated with lower quit intentions and greater addiction (Yang et al., 2022; Selby & Zawertailo, 2022).

Peer influence emerged as a powerful determinant of smoking behavior, with 92.6% of participants reporting that their friends smoked. According to social learning theory, peer and social networks significantly shape both cigarette initiation and maintenance (Carter et al., 2015; Özvurmaz & Yavaş, 2018). In this study, the most frequently reported reason for smoking initiation was “pleasure and enjoyment,” underscoring that smoking behavior is not solely driven by nicotine addiction but also by psychosocial and social interactional factors.

A significant proportion of participants recognized the health risks of smoking (74.1%) and considered cessation beneficial (94.4%). These findings are consistent with national and global studies. For instance, WHO data indicate that 89.8% of adults accept smoking as a cause of serious disease (WHO, 2016). Similarly, Gözüm and Çapık (2014) reported that higher perceived benefits within the framework of the Health Belief Model positively influencing cessation behaviors. The high level of health consciousness observed in this study suggests an advantage for motivation in future cessation interventions.

An important finding was that perceived severity was higher among females and younger participants. Prior literature has recommended that women take smoking-related health risks more seriously than men (Berberoğlu et al., 2019; Merih et al., 2021). Additionally, participants with higher levels of nicotine addiction reported greater perceptions of severity, indicating that as addiction increases, the salience of health risks becomes more evident. This aligns with the results of Carter et al. (2015) and Yang et al. (2022), who observed that individuals with higher nicotine addiction tend to perceive health consequences more concretely.

Perceived barriers were found to be relatively low, especially regarding social exclusion or stigma. However, economic factors (the cost of cigarettes) were found to be the most frequently cited obstacle. This finding highlights the potential deterrent role of taxation policies on smoking behavior in Türkiye. Consistent with this, Korkut and Sevinç (2021) also reported that financial constraints can stimulate cessation initiatives.

Regarding nicotine addiction, most participants were classified as very low dependent (59.2%), with a low mean FTND score (2.61 ± 2.62). This suggests that groups with relatively higher educational levels, such as university staff, may exhibit lower levels of dependence (Özvurmaz & Yavaş, 2018). However, the presence of a smaller subgroup with high reliance underscores the need for more intensive interventions tailored to these individuals.

Significant associations were identified between age of smoking initiation, health status, nicotine dependence, and self-effectiveness. Notably, those who initiated smoking after age 18 reported higher levels of dependence and poorer perceived health. While previous literature often emphasizes that earlier initiation increases dependence (Carter et al., 2015; Yang et al., 2022), the opposite pattern was observed in this study. This discrepancy may reflect contextual factors specific to adult participants, such as occupational stress, workload, and social interactions encountered during early adulthood.

The association between self-efficacy and smoking initiation age suggests that belief in one's capacity to quit plays a critical role in smoking behavior. Previous studies by Gözüm & Çapık (2014) and Kurcer & Erdoğan (2020) similarly found that higher self-effectiveness promotes cessation and serves as a protective factor against continued smoking. These findings reinforce the need for cessation programs to integrate self-effectiveness-enhancing strategies

The extremely high rate of smoking among peers (92.6%) further confirms the powerful impact of social networks on smoking behavior. This result is consistent with findings by Özvurmaz & Yavaş (2018) and Berberoğlu et al. (2019), who reported that having friends or relatives who smoke significantly increases initiation risk.

Economic barriers, especially the high cost of cigarettes, emerged as an important factor perceived by participants. Evidence from Türkiye suggests that tax increases implemented in 2024 have reduced tobacco use (Akkaya & Özmen, 2025). Similarly, WHO's 2024 report highlights the strong influence of price policies on cessation, especially in middle-income countries

These findings point to the potential role of strengthening social support mechanisms and promoting non-smoking peer groups as key strategies in cessation initiatives.

This research has several limitations. The relatively small sample size (n=54) and restriction to a single university limit the generalizability of the findings. The voluntary participation design may attract individuals with greater awareness of smoking-related issues. In addition, reliance on self-reported data introduces potential bias, including social desirability effects. Nevertheless, the application of the Health Belief Model provides a comprehensive framework for exploring the relationship between tobacco addiction and health perceptions, which represents a notable strength of the study.

Conclusion

This study evaluated tobacco addiction and health-related behaviors of academic and administrative university staff within the framework of the Health Belief Model. The findings revealed that most participants were aware of the health risks of smoking, believed in the benefits of cessation, and exhibited low levels of nicotine addiction. However, smoking behavior was strongly influenced by peer networks, and higher levels of addiction were associated with heightened perceptions of health risks. Self-efficacy emerged as a critical determinant of cessation behavior, suggesting that interventions should focus on increasing individuals' confidence in their ability to quit.

In light of these findings, cessation programs targeting university employees should adopt multidimensional approaches that address social influences and strengthen self-efficacy, while also taking advantage of policy measures that restrict access to tobacco products and increase economic deterrents.

For future research, multi-center studies involving various universities are recommended to improve generalizability. More balanced samples that include a higher proportion of male personnel would enable clearer examination of gender differences, while longitudinal designs could offer valuable insights into cessation trajectories. Finally, integrating psychosocial interventions that enhance self-efficacy and mitigate peer influences into cessation programs may significantly improve their effectiveness

Limitations

This study was limited to academic and administrative personnel at a single university, which restricts the generalizability of the findings. Future research should implement multi-center designs involving different universities to enhance external validity. More balanced samples that include male employees are recommended to allow for a clarifying examination of gender differences. Additionally, longitudinal studies would be valuable for monitoring cessation behaviors over time.

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